

VISCOSITY OF MIXED SOLUTIONS CONTAINING THREE AND FOUR IONIC SPECIES

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Viscosity of two binary electrolyte mixtures with common cations and two without common ions (each in three different proportions) as well as the viscosity values for solutions of three simple electrolytes are reported. Onsager and Fuoss' limiting law for mixed ionic solutions has been established in these cases and an equation of the Jones and Dole type applied to the results. The coefficient of the square root term 'A' has been shown to be a linear function of composition. The same is true of the coefficient of the linear term 'B', except in the case of NaCl-BaCl₂ mixtures, whose results are taken from a previous paper. The additive principle is not applicable to the viscosity of a mixed solution of two electrolytes, the observed values being systematically too low.

The variation in viscosity with concentration of solutions containing more than two kinds of ions has been worked out mathematically by Onsager and Fuoss (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2689). The viscosity variation of solutions containing two salts was studied experimentally by Chakravarti and Prasad (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 557). The present work is an extension of the same. The pairs examined will be evident from the tables. In these studies in any particular set, the ratio of the concentrations of two salts was fixed and change in viscosity was noted with change in total molecular concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental technique and procedure have been described in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 301). The viscometer used had a capillary of 10 cm. length, 0.028 cm. diameter with an upper bulb of 5 c.c. capacity. The approximate time of efflux for water was 29 mins. No kinetic energy or surface tension correction was considered necessary. Three readings for the time of flow were taken with a Venner time switch, graduated in tenths of seconds, agreeing with one another within 0.2 second. The time for water was determined before and after each solution. The pycnometers used were of about 64 and 55 c.c. capacity. Double distilled water was used in all the experiments. The thermostat was maintained at 35 ± 0.005 . The error in viscosity measurements is expected to be less than 3 parts in 10,000.

Chemicals used were of the highest possible quality. Standard solutions of the dry single salts were prepared and their strength verified gravimetrically. Mixtures having the two salts in any proportion were prepared by mixing the required volume of the two standard solutions. Mixtures were then diluted to decrease the total concentration to the required level.

In the case of single salt solutions as well as of all mixed solutions in which the proportion of the two salts were fixed, $\frac{\eta/\eta_0 - 1}{\sqrt{c}}$ plotted against $\sqrt{c}$ gave straight lines,

which means that mixture of two salts, if their proportion is fixed, behaves like single salts. Thus for all these cases the equation

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

holds good. In this equation η/η_0 is the relative (with respect to water at the same temperature) viscosity of the solution corresponding to the total concentration, *c* i.e. ($c_1 + c_2$) in g. moles per litre and 'A' and 'B' are constants. As expected, the equation is not applicable in some cases up to the highest concentrations measured.

In the following tables (I and II) η/η_0 (obs.) stands for observed relative viscosity and η/η_0 (calc.) for the relative viscosity calculated from an equation of the type shown above.

TABLE I.

$$\left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{obs.}) - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{calc.}) \right] \times 10^4 \text{ corresponding to conc. :}$$

Comp. of the solute.	A × 10 ⁵ .	B × 10 ⁵ .	0.01.	0.02.	0.03.	0.04.	0.05.	0.06.	0.07.	0.09.	0.12.	0.16.	0.20.
Pure K ₂ SO ₄ .	20	17.0	-3	-3	+2	+1	+2	0	+0	—	—	—	—
Pure KCl	8	0.0	0	-1	0	+4	-1	0	-3	—	—	—	—
Pure NaNO ₃	7	6.0	0	0	-1	+1	+0	+1	+1	—	—	—	—
[K ₂ SO ₄]:[KCl] =3:1	17	12.0	-3	-3	-2	0	+2	+2	+2	—	—	—	—
[K ₂ SO ₄]:[KCl] =1:1	14	8.0	-3	+2	+1	0	+1	+2	+2	—	—	—	—
[K ₂ SO ₄]:[KCl] =1:3	11	4.0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	+2	+3	—	—	—	—
[NaNO ₃]:[NaCl] =3:1	7	7.0	+3	+3	0	+1	-2	-2	-2	-12	-11	-13	-13
[NaNO ₃]:[NaCl] =1:1	7	8.0	0	-2	-2	0	-2	0	-1	-6	-7	-6	-11
[NaNO ₃]:[NaCl] =1:3	5	8.75	+2	0	+2	-1	-2	-3	-1	-2	-7	-5	-8

TABLE II.

$$\left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{obs.}) - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{calc.}) \right] \times 10^4 \text{ corresponding to conc. :}$$

Comp. of the solute.	A × 10 ⁵ .	B × 10 ⁵ .	0.01.	0.02.	0.03.	0.04.	0.05.	0.07.	0.10.	0.15.	0.20.
[NaNO ₃]:[KCl]=3:1	7	4.2	+1	-1	-3	0	0	0	0	0	0
[NaNO ₃]:[KCl]=1:1	7	3.1	-2	0	-1	0	-1	0	+3	+1	+3
[NaNO ₃]:[KCl]=1:3	7	1.5	-2	0	-1	0	-1	0	+1	-1	-3
[NaNO ₃]:[HCl]=3:1	5	5.8	-3	-4	-3	-2	0	+2	+1	+1	0
[NaNO ₃]:[HCl]=1:1	5	5.8	-3	-3	-1	0	-1	-1	+1	+5	+7
[NaNO ₃]:[HCl]=1:3	6	6.0	-3	-3	-2	0	-2	-2	-1	+2	+2

The observed value at any concentration corresponding to any proportion of the salts for which the experiment has been done, can be easily found out. The viscosity of a solution of NaNO_3 and HCl in equimolecular proportion having a total concentration of 0.05 can be calculated from the equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + 5 \times 10^3 \sqrt{0.05} + 5.8 \times 10^{-2} \times 0.05 = 1.0040.$$

Since the difference between the $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (obs.) and $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (calc.) = -1×10^{-4} , the observed value of $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1.0039$.

The examination of the tables shows that for any salt pair, the values of A and B go on changing with the proportion of one of them. In the figure both A and B have been plotted against molar percentage composition $\left(\frac{c_1}{c_1+c_2} \times 100\right)$ of one of the solutes. It is evident from the plot that A is a linear function in molar percentage composition in all cases. The plots for B also show a similar linearity except in the case of pure BaCl_2 in NaCl - BaCl_2 mixture. Some of the data for these plots have been taken from Chakravarti and Prasad's paper (*loc. cit.*).

The next question is whether the increase in viscosity due to two solutes can be considered to be additive, or not. If the increase was simply additive then the viscosity of a solution having a concentration of c_1 with respect to salt No. 1 and c_2 with respect to salt No. 2 would be given by the equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A_1\sqrt{c_1} + A_2\sqrt{c_2} + B_1c_1 + B_2c_2.$$

Actually it is given by the equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c_1+c_2} + B(c_1+c_2),$$

where $A = A_1 \cdot \frac{c_1}{c_1 + c_2} + A_2 \cdot \frac{c_2}{c_1 + c_2}$ and $B = \frac{B_1 c_1}{c_1 + c_2} + \frac{B_2 c_2}{c_1 + c_2}$, because both A and B are linear in composition of the solute (B is not linear in NaCl-BaCl₂ mixtures).

This is enough to show that the increase is not additive. The following table will make it clearer. $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (a) means the viscosity calculated according to simple additive principle. $\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}$ (calc.) means the relative viscosity calculated in previous tables.

TABLE III.

$\left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{obs}) - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{calc}) \right] \times 10^4$ are shown outside parenthesis and $\left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (\text{obs}) - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} (a) \right] \times 10^4$ in parenthesis.

Comp. of the solute.	$c=0.01$.	0.02.	0.03.	0.04.	0.05.	0.06.	0.07.
[NaCl]:[BaCl ₂]=3:1	-2(-9)	0(-10)	0(-13)	+3(-14)	0(-20)	0(-23)	-1(-27)
[NaCl]:[MgCl ₂]=4:1	+1(-1)	0(-4)	+1(-1)	-1(-6)	-1(-5)	+1(-3)	0(-3)
[K ₂ SO ₄]:[KCl]=3:1	-3(-8)	-3(-11)	-2(-12)	0(-12)	+2(-12)	+2(-13)	+2(-15)
[K ₂ SO ₄]:[NaCl]=1:3	-1(-7)	-1(-10)	0(-11)	-1(-14)	0(-16)	+2(-16)	+3(-14)
[NaNO ₃]:[NaCl]=3:1	+3(0)	+3(0)	0(-5)	+1(-3)	-2(-8)	-2(-7)	-2(-8)

The maximum experimental error in relative measurements is 3×10^{-4} . So it is evident that the observed viscosity is distinctly lower than that demanded by the additivity principle in most solutions. The difference goes on increasing as concentration increases. This has its parallel in the transference numbers (Wagner and Kuchler, *Physikal. Z.*, 1929, 30, 623; Longworth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1897) and specific conductivity (Bray and Hurt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 781).

It seems that Asmus (*Ann. Physik*, 1939, Sept. pp. 166-182) working on CuSO₄-H₂SO₄ mixture has come more or less to similar results as ours. On account of the continuance of the war the author has not been able to see the paper in original.

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